

Tutorial Series on Java Framework for Evolutionary Computation and Decision Making

Tutorial 12: A tool for generating reference pairwise comparisons for benchmarking interactive methods

Michał K. Tomczyk

Institute of Computing Science, Poznan University of Technology, Poznań, Poland

This document is part of a tutorial series on JECDM. URL: www.jecdm.cs.put.poznan.pl, email: jecdm@cs.put.poznan.pl.
The framework version used when preparing the document: 1.05.30.06.2025 (Java v. 17.0; IntelliJ IDEA 2023.3.8).

Abstract

This tutorial discusses a new tool for generating reference pairwise comparisons for benchmarking interactive methods. It can be deemed a supplement to the work on Evolutionary Rejection Sampling (“Tutorial 10: Evolutionary Rejection Sampling”).

Keywords: JECDM, pairwise comparisons, generating reference data

Contents

1 Introduction	1
2 Creating reference data	1
3 Loading reference data	4

1. Introduction

This tutorial showcases a simple tool for pre-constructing reference models of artificial Decision Makers (DMs) and synthetic data on pairwise comparisons they conducted. Note that the update is considered a supplement to the work on *Evolutionary Rejection Sampling* (see the “Tutorial 10: Evolutionary Rejection Sampling” tutorial document). The data construction processing is based on the procedure introduced in the project referred to in that document. Hence, the Reader is recommended to examine that article before proceeding.

2. Creating the data

Source package:
`t11_t20.t12_generating_reference_pcs.Tutorial1`

Tutorial 1 showcases how to employ the developed tool to pre-construct data on artificial DM and their synthetic pairwise comparisons. The main class is *Experimentation.tools.feedbackgenerators.PCsDataGenerator*. The tutorial assumes that the data to be generated is contextually given:

- different shapes of the Pareto optimal part of the objective space (convex and concave spherical Pareto fronts),
- different numbers of objectives (from 2 to 5),
- different models of an artificial DM used to compare selected pairs of solutions (weighted sum and Chebyshev models).

The tool generates the data and stores it in a readable text file.

The code is relatively well-commented. Therefore, it will not be elaborated extensively in this document. Nonetheless, it is brought here for the Reader’s convenience.

Let’s start with Listing 1, which begins the configuration of the tool. It showcases how to define the experimental settings, i.e., contexts (similarly similar to how it is done when designing experiments in JECDM).

Listing 1: Configuring the tool #1

```
// First, let's instantiate the params
// container:
PCsDataGenerator.Params p = new
    PCsDataGenerator.Params();

// Now, let's specify the context (
// equivalent to defining experimental
// scenarios when designing experiments);
p._keys = new String[]{
    "SHAPE", // Assume that the reference
// alternatives for comparisons will be
// drawn from various Pareto fronts (
// shapes)
    "M", // Also, assume that the
// dimensionality may vary (denoted by M)
    "DM" // Finally, assume that the DM's
// artificial model may vary
```

Email address: michal.tomczyk@cs.put.poznan.pl (Michał K. Tomczyk)

URL: www.cs.put.poznan.pl/mtomczyk (Michał K. Tomczyk)

```

};
10 // Below, example realizations of the above
    keys can be found:
p._values = new String[][]
{
    {"CONVEX", "concave"}, // note that the
        key and value will be converted to
        uppercase
15 {"2", "3", "4", "5"},
    {"WSM", "CHEBYSHEV"} // WSM = weighted
        linear model; Chebyshev = weighted
        Chebyshev model
};

// The tool allows specifying keys that
    will share the same alternative sets
    constructed and processed by the
20 // tool. For instance, the "DM" key does
    not affect the solution space anyway;
    thus, the alternatives can be
// shared for all realizations of this key.
    It will boost the processing efficiency
    . IMPORTANT NOTE:
// the "common" keys must be specified as
    the last ones in the "_keys" param.
p._keysCommonForAlternatives = new String
    [{"DM"}];

25 // Similarly to the experimentation module
    (designing experiments), the Cartesian
    product of all key values
// defines all experimental settings. One
    may, however, easily disable (exclude)
    some of them. In the context
// of this tutorial, there is no reason to
    apply a "DM=WSM" to concave Pareto
    fronts (as such DM should always
// point to extreme solutions). The below
    line disables all such settings:
p._scenarioDisablingConditions = new
    ScenarioDisablingConditions(new String
    [{"SHAPE", "DM"},
30 new String[]{"CONCAVE", "CHEBYSHEV"}]);

```

Next, Listing 2 fills some other relevant parameters.

Listing 2: Configuring the tool #2

```

p._trials = 100; // Set number of test
    repeats within a scenario to 100
int interactions = 10; // Consider the
    number of interactions equal 10

// The below field allows specifying the
    number of interactions associated with a
    scenario being processed
5 // (see the "INoInteractionsProvider"
    interface). This example assumes a
    constant number of interactions for
// each scenario (and its test run).
p._noInteractionsProvider = new Constant(
    interactions);

```

```

// As with the experimentation module, not
    all characters are allowed in the key/
    values labels. The below field
10 // allows specifying additional allowed
    characters.
p._extraAllowedCharacters = new Character
    [{"_', '-'}];

// Let's specify a random number generator
    to be used by this tool:
p._R = new MersenneTwister64(0);

```

Then, Listing 3 outlines how to define a way of generating reference alternatives from which pairs of solutions should be selected to form reference pairs to be presented and compared by the DM. Furthermore, the code demonstrates how to define data on the objective space (span and optimization directions).

Listing 3: Configuring the tool #3

```

// The below parameter is expected to be
    supplied with the implementation of "
    IAlternativesProvider," which is
// supposed to return alternatives sets (
    array of array of alternatives)
    contextually to the (i) scenario being
// processed. The first dimension (array)
    refers to different interaction numbers
    (index of 0 refers to the first
// interaction, of 1 to the second, etc.);
    the second dimension represents
    associated alternatives. In this
5 // example, a straightforward
    implementation named "FromShapeProvider"
    is used. It allows for defining
// the reference shape (alternatives,
    defined as a matrix of their
    performances: double [][]) and a
    rescaling
// function that allows for rescaling the
    reference shape given the interaction
    number, which may be employed
// to account for convergence towards the
    PF in subsequent interactions.
p._alternativesProvider = new
    FromShapeProvider("M", 100000,
10 (scenario, n, m, R) -> { // Should return
        a reference performance matrix given
        the "SHAPE" of
// the scenario being currently processed
    if (scenario.getKeyValuesMap().get("
        SHAPE").getValue().equals("CONVEX"))
        return ReferencePointsFactory.
            getUniformRandomRPsOnConvexSphere(
            n, m, R);
        else return ReferencePointsFactory.
            getUniformRandomRPsOnConcaveSphere
            (n, m, R);
15 },
// The below lines define how the
    reference shape is rescaled given the

```

```

    interaction number
// (here, a simple linear interpolation
    from 2.0 (the first interaction) to
    1.0 (the last interaction)
// is employed).
(scenario, interaction, noInteractions, e
) -> {
20   double rM = 2.0d - (interaction / (
        double) (noInteractions - 1));
    if (scenario.getKeyValuesMap().get("
        SHAPE").getValue().equals("CONVEX"))
        for (double[] a : e) for (int i = 0;
            i < a.length; i++) a[i] *= rM;
    else
25     for (double[] a : e)
        for (int i = 0; i < a.length; i
            ++) a[i] = ((a[i] - 1.0d) * rM
                ) + rM;
});

// The range provider may be specified to
    define how a solution space is bounded
    for a scenario being processed.
// Here, it is specified that the solution
    space is bounded by the [0, 2]^M
    hypercube. These ranges are employed
30 // to define the normalization functions
    that can be used, e.g., to normalize
    alternatives' performance vectors
// when being evaluated by the artificial
    DM.
p._rangesProvider = new RangesProvider("M",
    M -> Range.getDefaultRanges(M, 2.0d));

// The field below should be instantiated
    with an object responsible for
    delivering criteria (objectives) types.
35 // Here, a boolean["M"] vector is returned
    (instantiated with false, by default,
    which indicates criteria to be
// minimized).
p._criteriaTypesProvider = new Cost("M");

```

Then, Listing 4 concerns formulating the way the model of an artificial DM is established, solution pairs are selected, and specifies parses used to store the data on the models and the pairs.

Listing 4: Configuring the tool #4

```

// //The below field must be instantiated
    with an implementation of the "
    IDMMModelProvider" interface,
// responsible for defining the internal
    model of an artificial DM, given the
    scenario being currently processed.
// The tutorial uses a default "
    DMMModelProvider" implementation.
p._dmModelProvider = new DMMModelProvider<>(
    "M", (DMMModelProvider.IInternalModel<
    AbstractValueInternalModel>)
5   (scenario, t, M, normalizations, R) -> {

```

```

// Let's set the alpha value for the L-
    norm (contextual to the "DM" key).
double alpha = 1.0d; // Linear model
if (scenario.getKeyValuesMap().get("DM").
    getValue().equals("CHEBYSHEV"))
    alpha = Double.POSITIVE_INFINITY; //
    Chebyshev model

// Return a suitably parameterized L-norm
return new LNorm(WeightsGenerator.
    getNormalizedWeightVector(M, R),
    alpha, normalizations);
});

// The model writer (parser) must be
    specified. The code uses a default
    LNormWriterParser, dedicated to L-norms.
p._modelWriter = new LNormWriterParser();

// The below field must be supplied with an
    implementation of "
    IReferenceAlternativesSelector," which
    is supposed
20 // to return indices pointing to
    alternatives that the DM must compare to
    form pairwise comparisons. This
    tutorial
// uses GammaIndicesForPCs, which favors
    better alternatives (in the view of the
    oracle, i.e., artificial DM)
// the later the interaction is (see the
    associated article for details).
p._refAlternativesSelector = new
    GammaIndicesForPCs(2.0d);

// The alternatives writer (parser) must be
    specified. The code uses a default
    AlternativeWriterParser.
p._alternativeWriter = new
    AlternativeWriterParser();

```

Finally, code 5 instantiates and executes the tool. The results are supposed to be stored in the "PCs.txt" file in the same directory as the tutorial's main class.

Listing 5: Configuring the tool #5

```

try
{
    // Let's specify that the resulting data
    will be stored in this package in the
    "PCs.txt" file.
    Path path = FileUtils.
        getPathRelatedToClass(Tutorial1.class,
            "Tutorials", "src", File.
            separatorChar);
5   p._filePath = path.toString() + File.
        separatorChar + "PCs.txt";
    // Let's create the tool instance and run
    it.
    PCsDataGenerator DG = new
        PCsDataGenerator(p);
    DG.process();
}

```

10

```
} catch (Exception | IOException e)
{
    throw new RuntimeException(e);
}
```

Similarly to other tools in the experimentation module, the processing provides informative logs to the console. As an example, Figure 1 depicts the logs printed when the processing started. Next, Figure 2 illustrates a snippet from the resulting text file (“PCs.txt”).

3. Loading the data

Source package:
t11_t20.t12_generating_reference_pcs.Tutorial2

Finally, the *Tutorial2* class concerns loading the pre-constructed data generated by the runnable in *Tutorial1*. It also visualizes the data (pairwise comparisons and how the DM perceives the objective space) associated with a selected test run for a 2-dimensional scenario concerning a convex shape of the Pareto front and a weighted sum model for the artificial DM. Since the code is straightforward, it is not brought here for the sake of conciseness. Yet, for convenience, Figure 3 depicts the expected visualization product,

```

[30.6.2025 13:24:14:108]: Processing started
[30.6.2025 13:24:14:116]: Attempting to create the file = D:\
[30.6.2025 13:24:14:121]: Processing scenario = SHAPE_CONVEX_M_2_DM_WSM started
[30.6.2025 13:24:14:121]: New set(s) of alternatives are to be constructed
[30.6.2025 13:24:14:390]: Processing trials started
[30.6.2025 13:24:14:391]: Processing trial = 0
[30.6.2025 13:24:14:406]: Evaluating and sorting alternatives according to the DM's model
[30.6.2025 13:24:14:890]: Constructing pairwise comparisons
[30.6.2025 13:24:14:896]: Processing trial = 1
[30.6.2025 13:24:14:896]: Evaluating and sorting alternatives according to the DM's model
[30.6.2025 13:24:15:134]: Constructing pairwise comparisons
[30.6.2025 13:24:15:136]: Processing trial = 2

```

Figure 1: Expected console output (processing)

```

SHAPE_CONVEX_M_2_DM_WSM
Ranges entries = "2"
Range 0 = "0.0 2.0"
Range 1 = "0.0 2.0"
Criteria types entries = "2"
Criterion 0 = "false"
Criterion 1 = "false"
T = "0"
L-NORM;1.0;2;0.00396586600285731;0.9960341339971427
Interaction = "0"
Alternative = "A_0_92693"
State = "NOT_PREFERRED"
A_0_92693;1;0.9960252034241303;2;8.039147125771251E-11;1.9999820677367028
Alternative = "A_0_12913"
State = "PREFERRED"
A_0_12913;1;0.8361061651424636;2;0.025966202154584783;1.67876711724357

```

Figure 2: Snippet from the result file

Figure 3: Example result (2-dimensional case)